

Author details: Mr. Mohammad Rahaman Khan, Vignan Institute of Agriculture and Technology, School of Agriculture and Food Technology, Vignan's Foundation for Science, Technology and Research, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh- India.

Herbicide Residue: Environmental Implications and Management, A Review

I. Introduction

Weeds are one of the major threats to the agriculture for ages. Globally, a number of chemicals are tested and used for weed management from time immemorial. However, the major shift in the use of agricultural chemicals was observed after World War II. Now, the chemists and agronomists are overly optimistic about the use of agricultural chemicals in solving the pest problems (Trappe *et al.*, 1984). Introduction of 2,4-Dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D) in the 1940s totally revolutionized the agriculture and started the era of chemical weed control (Choudhury *et al.* 2016). Until 2016, more than 2000 herbicides belonging to 15 different modes of action were introduced in the global market (Choudhury *et al.*, 2016). Economic viability and easy application make it one of the most common tools for the weed management in modern-day agriculture. Intensity of utilization was further increased with adoption of conservation agriculture practices and herbicide-resistant genetically modified crops.

In fact, the use of herbicide increases the profitability of the farm but at the expense of ecosystem functions. It is now apparent that use of these herbicides not only has unforeseen impact on the environment but also severely impacts our soil microflora (Trappe *et al.*, 1984). Of late, raises the concern that only small fractions of pesticide reach to the target organisms, leading to potential impact in soil and water and ultimately affecting the human, crop and animal health (Pimentel, 1995). Although it is true that use of pesticide increases the crop production but at the same time it acts as a double-edged weapon, because since the onset of green revolution, nearly 800,000 people in the developing countries have died due to pesticides (Devi *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, nearly, 20,000 people in the developing countries die every year due to pesticide consumption through food (Bhardwaj and Sharma, 2013).

Herbicides, as the most commonly used pesticides, can threaten agricultural safety and influence the water and soil resources, human and animal health, food safety, non-target plants, and ecosystem function and structure. In recent years, numerous incidents have been reported about the negative impacts of herbicides and their residues on different crops like cereals, vegetables, oil plants, *etc.* The continuous use of herbicides leads to the problem of soil persistency that causes far reaching environmental consequences. The longer persistence of herbicide in soil poses a hazard to subsequent land use, which is undesirable. The increased

awareness towards the adverse effects of herbicide residues on human health and environment caused a significant shift towards the adoption of mitigation strategies of herbicide residues in soil as well as in plants. Keeping these facts, the effect of herbicidal residue on environment and their management is studied.

Fig.1: Relative use of pesticides in world and India

Presently, herbicides use in India is meagre as compared to the global scenario (Fig. 1) (Vision 2050-NRCWS, 2015). The consumption of insecticides takes the major share (>two-third), while the herbicides use is only <20 %. However, the herbicide use is expected to increase by 15-20 % per annum in the future. The herbicides registered in India are of low mammalian toxicity, and most of these are applied early in season, so that the waiting period can be attained by the harvest time. However, herbicides persist in the soil long enough to produce the residual effect. There is every chance of herbicide molecule being transported to different compartments of environment, including ground and surface water. There is always a potential risk of food and water contamination due to herbicide use. Not only the indiscriminate use of herbicide affects the environment, but it also influences the weed biology adversely. Herbicide application is more common in wheat crop (44 %), followed by rice (31 %), plantation crop (10 %), soybean (4 %), and other crops (11 %) (Fig. 2, Sondhia, 2014).

Fig.2: Relative use of herbicides in various crops in India

II. Fate of herbicide after its application

Herbicides undergo different decomposition processes after their application based on surrounding environmental and edaphic factors (Fig.3) viz.;

1. Microbial decomposition

Microbial decomposition is one of the most important methods by which herbicides are decomposed in soil. Microorganisms in the soil metabolize organic herbicides either aerobically (with oxygen) or anaerobically (without oxygen). In most cases, the microorganisms consume the herbicide molecules and utilize them as a source of energy and nutrients for growth and reproduction.

2. Chemical decomposition

Decomposition of herbicides in the soil purely by chemical (non-biological) processes is common for some herbicides. Decomposition may occur as the result of processes such as oxidation-reduction and hydrolysis.

3. Soil adsorption

Adsorption is an important factor that makes herbicides unavailable for uptake by plants. Adsorption is the attraction or adhesion of molecules or ions to the surface of soil particles (colloids). Almost all soil-applied herbicides are adsorbed to some extent. Weed control is inversely proportional to how much herbicide is adsorbed to the soil.

4. Volatilization

Volatilization of herbicides is the vaporization of herbicide to a gaseous form. Herbicides vary widely in volatility and loss to the atmosphere as a gas. Herbicide volatilization increases as the temperature rises. Usually, very little volatilization occurs once the herbicide is mixed into the soil either by mechanical incorporation or rainfall. Volatility loss is greater when herbicides are applied to a moist soil surface than a dry soil surface.

5. Photodecomposition

Photodecomposition is the degradation of herbicides by sunlight. In the photodecomposition process, the herbicide molecule absorbs energy from sunlight, causing chemical reactions that result in herbicide inactivation. Certain dinitroaniline herbicides, for example, are readily degraded by sunlight if left on the soil surface. Soil incorporation will reduce or eliminate photodecomposition.

6. Plant uptake and metabolism

Plant roots may absorb (take up) herbicides from soils and plant foliage may intercept foliar-applied chemicals. Crops and plants tolerant to a herbicide often metabolize the chemical into non-toxic substances. Differential metabolism is often the basis for herbicide selectivity.

7. Leaching

Leaching is the movement of herbicides through soil by water. Leaching may occur in any direction (down, up, sideways), depending on water movement, but usually refers to the downward movement of a herbicide as water percolates down through the soil following precipitation or irrigation. The movement of a herbicide by leaching is important to weed control effectiveness, herbicide carryover, and the potential for environmental problems.

8. Surface runoff

Intact herbicide molecules may be carried by surface water flow. They may be adsorbed to soil particles that move, dissolved in surface runoff water, or carried intact by surface runoff water (Sondhia, 2018).

Fig.3: Fate of herbicide after its application

III. Persistency of herbicides

The herbicides provide their actions as long they persist in the soil and environment. The effective life of an herbicide is considered as its persistence. The residual life of herbicides

is expressed in terms of their half-life or period of persistence. Herbicides vary in their potential to persist in the soil (Table 1).

Longer persistency may be desirable for some long duration crops like sugarcane while short-term persistency is desirable to the crops under intensive cropping systems. Short-term persistency is desirable for escaping the phytotoxicity in the succeeding crops in the intensive cropping systems (Sondhia, 2020). Thus, herbicide should be selected based on the crop and cropping system.

Table 1: Persistence of herbicides in soil under Indian tropical conditions

Herbicide	Persistence in soil (days)	Herbicide	Persistence in soil (days)
Atrazine	45–150	Oxadiazon	56–125
Alachlor	60–90	Pyrazosulfuron ethyl	35–60
2,4-D	45–90	Pretilachlor	30–90
Butachlor	100	Pendimethalin	60–200
Dithiopyr	90–150	Tralkoxydim	28–45
Fluazifop-P-butyl	30–90	Thiobencarb	28–60
Isoproturon	90–120	Oxyfluorfen	60–80
Imazosulfuron	60–90	Imazethapyr	90–240
Metoxuron	10–70	Metolachlor	40–190
Metribuzin	20–100		

IV. Methods for detecting herbicide residues

There are some different analytical methods for detecting herbicide residues in the environment. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), thin-layer chromatography (TLC), high performance liquid chromatography/ mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS), gas chromatography/ mass spectrometry (GC-MS), high performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS), and capillary electrophoresis are from essential and commonly used analytical methods herbicide residues evaluating studies in soil. Successful detection of herbicide residues from different media has been reported using analytical methods. However, these methods are complicated, expensive, time-consuming, require specialized equipment, different solvents with high purity, and extraction techniques for separating herbicide residues from the soil (Wang *et al.*, 2019).

Besides analytical methods, there are various bioassay methods to identify, detect, and quantify herbicide residues in the environment. In plant bioassay, as the standard type of bioassay method, sensitive plants are used as reliable bio-indicators for detecting unknown concentrations of herbicides in soil (Table 2). These sensitive plants should be responsive to low concentrations of herbicides in the soil. Understanding and evaluating these responses depends on the herbicide's nature and mode of action and the tested plant's susceptibility. Germination inhibitions, fresh or dry biomass of the roots or shoots, heights of the plant, root lengths, photosynthetic inhibition, the content of chlorophyll, *etc.*, are among the critical plant measurements bioassays (Kadivar *et al.*, 2023).

Table 2: Bioassay materials used for various groups of herbicides

Herbicides	Indicator species
Aliphatic halogenated acids (Dalapon)	Oats, millets, cucumber, barley, wheat, rice
Acetanilide (Alachlor, Metolachlor)	Cucumber, rye grass, crab grass
Benzofuran (Ethofumesate)	Cucumber, oats, foxtail, pig weed
Benzoic acid (Dicamba)	Beans, sorghum, cucumber
Diphenyl ether (oxyfluorfen)	Cucumber, crab grass
Phenoxy derivative (2,4-D)	Cotton, pig weed, tomato, mustard

V. Environmental Implications

Herbicide enters into the environment through application to plant/ or soil, drifts and vapours and are subjected to various reactions under different soil and environmental conditions. The contamination of the environment by herbicides depends upon factors like nature of herbicide, its persistence in the soil, bioaccumulation (biomagnification), amount used, and method of application.

1. Soil

Herbicides can significantly influence soil properties through both direct and indirect mechanisms. Direct effects include alterations in soil pH, organic matter content, and nutrient availability. For instance, glyphosate, a commonly used herbicide, has been shown to increase soil acidity, thereby reducing the availability of essential nutrients such as calcium and magnesium (Rose *et al.*, 2016). This acidification can lead to nutrient imbalance that adversely affects plant growth and soil health (Mishra *et al.*, 2017). Organic matter content in soil is another critical factor influenced by herbicidal application. Herbicides can reduce soil organic matter by inhibiting the growth of cover crops and other vegetation that contribute to organic matter accumulation (Rose *et al.*, 2016). This reduction in organic matter can degrade soil

structure and decrease its water-holding capacity, leading to increased soil erosion and reduced fertility (Meena *et al.*, 2016).

Indirect effects of herbicides involve changes in soil microbial communities and enzyme activities. Soil microorganisms play a vital role in nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition. Herbicides can disrupt these microbial communities, leading to reduced microbial biomass and diversity (Marfo *et al.*, 2019). For example, glyphosate has been found to inhibit the activity of soil enzymes involved in nitrogen and phosphorus cycling, which are crucial for maintaining soil fertility (Norton, 2013).

Fig.4: Overall distribution of glyphosate and amino methyl phosphonic acid in European Union top soils (0–15/20 cm)

Frequency of detection of glyphosate and AMPA ($\geq 0.05 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) in soils from different (A) EU countries (B) crop systems (C&D represents the concentrations). N – no. of samples tested, Np = no. of positive samples $\geq 0.05 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, G – glyphosate, A – AMPA (Amino Methyl Phosphonic Acid)

Glyphosate and/or AMPA ($\geq 0.05 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) were present in nearly half (45 %) of the soil samples, with 18 % of the tested soils containing both compounds. AMPA was the predominant form, being present in 42 % of the soils while glyphosate was present in 21 %. Both compounds were present at higher frequencies in northern soils, while eastern and southern regions generally had the most glyphosate and AMPA free soils ($\geq 0.05 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), respectively. At national levels, the frequency of soils with glyphosate ranged from 7 % in Poland to 53% in Portugal, while the frequency of soils with AMPA ranged from 17 % in Italy and Greece to 80% in Denmark (Fig. 4A). Samples from permanent crops and root crops had the highest frequency of soils with glyphosate and AMPA (30 and 52 %, respectively), and dry pulses and fodder crops the lowest for both compounds (5 and 29 %, respectively, see Fig. 4B).

The highest concentrations of glyphosate and AMPA in soil were observed in southern parts of the EU (Fig. 4C), suggesting higher application rates of glyphosate based herbicides in this region. Nevertheless, only concentrations of glyphosate were significantly higher in this region. Glyphosate and AMPA contents in soil were highest under permanent crops and lowest with dry pulses and fodder crops (Fig. 4D). These herbicidal residues in soil leading to less choice of crops and decrease in yields of several crops in EU region (Silva *et al.*, 2018).

2. Microbial Communities

Soil microbial communities are essential for nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition, playing a critical role in maintaining soil health and fertility. Herbicides can disrupt these communities, leading to reduced microbial biomass and diversity. For instance, glyphosate, a widely used herbicide, has been shown to interfere with the shikimate pathway in plants and microorganisms, impeding the production of aromatic amino acids and leading to shifts in microbial community composition (Van Bruggen *et al.*, 2021). This disruption can result in decreased soil heterotrophic respiration and the activity of organic matter-degrading microorganisms (Rose *et al.*, 2016). In Australia, studies have demonstrated that herbicide residues can persist in the soil, affecting microbial functions and overall soil health. Rose *et al.* (2019) found that herbicidal residues were detected in more than 30 % of paddocks surveyed, with potential impacts on soil microbial functions. These residues can lead to long-term changes in microbial community structure, reducing the abundance of beneficial microorganisms such as mycorrhizal fungi and nitrogen-fixing bacteria (Singh *et al.*, 2020).

The impact of herbicides on soil microbial communities can also vary depending on the type of herbicide and soil conditions. Some herbicides have been shown to reduce the population of soil microorganisms with transient inhibition lasting up to 7-10 days, while others may have no effect or even increase microbial populations (Sebiomo *et al.*, 2011). However, the overall trend indicates that herbicides have a negative impact on soil microbial diversity and function. Understanding the effects of herbicides on soil microbial communities is crucial for developing sustainable agricultural practices. By minimizing the use of herbicides and adopting alternative weed management strategies, it is possible to preserve soil health and maintain the ecological balance of soil microbial communities.

3. Crop

Rice: Sondhia and Dixit (2012) demonstrated that ethoxysulfuron dissipated at faster rate in plants and residues were found below $0.001 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ in grains and straw at harvest at 15-20 g ha^{-1} application rates. Imazosulfuron residues were found to be 0.009 and $0.039 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ at 50 and

60 g ha⁻¹ rates, respectively in rice and residues were not detected at 30-40 g ha⁻¹ in rice grains and straw (Sondhia 2007 and 2008).

Wheat: In a field experiment, residues of isoproturon were found to be 0.006, 0.041 and 0.022 µg g⁻¹ in postharvest soil, wheat grain and straw, respectively, while 0.021 and 0.096 µg g⁻¹ residues of clodinafop was present in soil and grain at higher level of application (Arora *et al.* 2017).

Herbicide residues in pulses

Terminal residues of pendimethalin were monitored in the green field peas and chickpea applied as pre-emergence herbicide at 750-185 g ha⁻¹ rates. Low pendimethalin residues were found in mature pea grains (0.004-BDL µg g⁻¹), and straw (0.007- 0.001 µg g⁻¹) at 750-185 g ha⁻¹ treatments, respectively (Sondhia, 2013).

Herbicide residues in oilseed crops

In a three seasons field trial conducted under West Bengal conditions, diclosulam residues were found to be below detectable level (BDL) in soybean plant samples irrespective of the treatment doses and the days in all seasons (Bhattacharyya *et al.*, 2012). The residues of imazethapyr in soil, soybean grains and straw were found 0.008, 0.102 and 0.301 µg g⁻¹, respectively at 100 g ha⁻¹ application rate (Sondhia, 2008).

4. Water

With the increasing use of herbicides for weed control, the applied herbicide may find its way into streams and underground water sources by runoff, drift and leaching mechanism (Sondhia 2008, 2009 and 2013). Many herbicides are routinely detected from the surface and ground water sources in developed countries like, USA, New Zealand, Australia, Canada, Japan and European countries. The most often detected herbicides above the prescribed maximum residues limits are 2,4-D, atrazine, cyanazine, carbaryl, simazine, bromacil, diuron, diazinon, prometon, metalachlor, dinoseb, picloram, metribuzin, metsulfuron, glyphosate, metolachlor, propanil, butachlor, pendimethalin, oxyfluorfen *etc.* Many herbicides are strictly banned or restricted such as butachlor, atrazine, pendimethalin, and paraquat in USA, and European countries due to their high concentration in the ground and surface water and potential health hazards to aquatic, animal and human lives.

In India, reports on monitoring and detection of herbicide residues in water are limited as compared to developed countries. Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl residue level of 0.0154 mg kg⁻¹ on 21st day and of 0.0023 mg kg⁻¹ on 35th day were detected in the underground water (Naveen *et al.*, 2012). Persistence and mobility of 2,4-D were found to be dependent on soil water content (Gupta *et al.*, 2012). The water samples collected from Singoor reservoir, Hyderabad were

found contaminated with residues of atrazine (BDL-1.056 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$). The concentration of atrazine residues in Osmansagar water was 0.056 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ during post-monsoon November 2005, and total pesticide residues together 3.369 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ (Reddy and Reddy, 2010). Residues of alachlor were detected up to 60 days in acidic, neutral and basic buffer solution fortified with 0.5 and 1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and residue were below the detection limit after 140 days in water different soils and no residues were detected after 80 days. The studies conducted at AICRP on weed control in water system revealed that butachlor residues were ranged between 0.001 to 0.093 mg l^{-1} in the water of rice field (AICRP 2009). Residues of paraquat were not detected after 20 days at 0.80 kg ha^{-1} application rates to control *Eichornia* but application of 1.8 kg ha^{-1} showed 0.069 and 0.028 mg l^{-1} residues in pond.

Fig.5: Frequency of pesticides detection from grab samples collected across all sites

Frequency (%) was determined based on the number of samples that were analysed for LC-MS, n = 268 (a); phenoxy herbicides n = 13 (b); and GC-MS, n = 80 (c)

The transport and potential toxicity of pesticides in Queensland (QLD) catchments from agricultural areas is a key concern for the Great Barrier Reef (GBR). In 2009, a pesticide monitoring program was established as part of the Australian and QLD Governments' Reef Plan (2009). Samples were collected at eight end of system sites (above the tidal zone) and three sub-catchment sites. From the 268 grab samples analysed using LC-MS (Fig. 5), seven different PSII herbicides were detected, with atrazine, hexazinone and tebuthiuron the most frequently detected pesticides (occurring in more than 50 % of samples). Ametryn was detected the least of the five priority PSII herbicides, being detected in less than 20 % of samples. Metolachlor, a plant growth inhibitor, frequently detected, occurring in approximately 30 % of samples. Thirteen samples were analysed for phenoxy acid herbicides from two sites, Barratta Creek and Sandy Creek (Fig. 5). The synthetic auxins, 2,4-D and MCPA were detected in more

than 90 % and 60 % of these samples, respectively. Another synthetic auxin, fluroxypyr, was also detected but in less than 10% of samples.

5. Non Target Organisms

The main intention of using herbicide is to keep weeds to below economically acceptable threshold, judged on the basis of the amount of damage that can be tolerated to crops. Most herbicides are specifically plant poisons and are not very toxic to animals, with few exceptions such as paraquat, which is toxic to animals. However, herbicides mainly affect population of birds, mammals, insects and other animals through changes in the nature of their habitat. Herbicides causes change in structure and abundance of non-crop plants in agro-ecosystem affecting food availability of granivorous birds, that eat weed seeds, and the food availability of birds that eat arthropods which rely mainly on non-crop plants for nourishment and habitat (Rahman, 2019).

Fishes:

In a study, Yadav *et al.* (2013) revealed the genotoxic potential of butachlor even at low dose level (1.0 mg kg^{-1}) and suggested that butachlor interferes with cellular activities in fishes at genetic level inducing chromosomal aberrations and suggested a serious concern towards the potential danger of butachlor for aquatic organisms. On comparing the effect of different herbicides, it was observed that the fish mortality was more with 2,4-DEE and paraquat than with glyphosate (Muniappa *et al.*, 1995). To evaluate the possible bio-accumulation of sulfosulfuron in the fishes, an experiment was conducted in glass aquarium for 90 days. Sulfosulfuron was applied to the aquariums at $25\text{-}100 \text{ g ha}^{-1}$. Residues of sulfosulfuron in the fishes were found $1.09\text{-}3.52 \text{ }\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ after 10 days and by 90 day's residues in the fishes were below the MRL (Sondhia, 2008).

In another indirect effect of herbicides on fishes, mortality was more with butachlor, followed by anilofos and oxyflourfen (Sondhia, 2012). Pretilachlor, penoxsulam and pyrazosulfuron- ethyl residues ranged between $0.0133, 0.0189$ and $0.063 \text{ }\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ at 30 days and dissipated to $<0.001, 0.017$ and 0.010 , respectively at 60 days respectively in fishes (Sondhia, 2012, 2013 and 2014). In another study, fishes (*Channa punctata*) were exposed for 10 days to sub lethal concentration ($1/5^{\text{th}}$ of static LC50) of butachlor. Residue of butachlor after 10 days were $0.1255 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ in gills, 0.3515 (bloch) liver in (bloch) liver, $0.3145 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ in kidney and $0.2350 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ in brain traces muscle of *Channa punctata*.

The results revealed that prolonged exposure to sub lethal concentrations led to increase in the accumulation of residues. The residues are accumulated in different tissues, causing

toxicity to the fishes which ultimately resulted in biomagnifications through the food chain (Tilak, 2007).

Pollinators:

Glyphosate, the primary herbicide used globally for weed control, targets the 5-enolpyruvylshikimate-3-phosphate synthase (EPSPS) enzyme in the shikimate pathway found in plants and some microorganisms. Thus, glyphosate may affect bacterial symbionts of animals living near agricultural sites, including pollinators such as bees. The honey bee gut microbiota is dominated by eight bacterial species that promote weight gain and reduce pathogen susceptibility. The gene encoding EPSPS is present in almost all sequenced genomes of bee gut bacteria, indicating that they are potentially susceptible to glyphosate. Glyphosate exposure of young workers increased mortality of bees subsequently exposed to the opportunistic pathogen *Serratia marcescens* (Motta *et al.*, 2018).

Human health:

Indirect effects of herbicides on human are not common in India. However, increasing incidences of acute herbicide self-poisoning by butachlor, fluchloralin, paraquat, 2,4-D, pendimethalin, glyphosate *etc.* are a significant problem in parts of Asia (Senarathna *et al.* 2009).

Due to paraquat low vapour pressure and the formation of large droplets, inhalation of paraquat spray used in the open environment has not been shown to cause any significant systemic toxicity; however, inhalational exposure to paraquat in confined spaces, such as a greenhouse, is known to be associated with fatal pulmonary disease. Irrespective of its route of administration in mammalian systems, paraquat is rapidly distributed in most tissues, with the highest concentration found in the lungs and kidneys. The compound accumulates slowly in the lungs via an energy dependent process. Excretion of paraquat, in its unchanged form, is biphasic, owing to lung accumulation and occurs largely in the urine and, to a limited extent, in the bile (Suntres, 2002). Poisoning with paraquat leads to both local and systemic effects.

The oxidative role of butachlor in intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, and consequent mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative DNA damage, and chromosomal breakage, which eventually triggers necrosis in human peripheral blood mononuclear (PBMN) cells is also reported (Dwivedi *et al.* 2012).

In an experiment, cultured human lymphocytes were exposed to three different concentrations (2.5, 5.0 and 10.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of fluchloralin for 24 and 48 hrs. to assess chromosomal aberrations. A significant dose-dependent increase of chromatid type aberration was observed in these cells. Multiple aberrations (MA) were scored at all concentrations after

48 hrs treatment. Higher concentrations of fluchloralin (20, 40 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) resulted in a significant dependent increase in number of micronucleated cells and showed genotoxic effects of fluchloralin in human cells (Panneerselvam *et al.* 1995).

Nair *et al.* (2005) demonstrated that 2,4-D is capable of inducing higher DNA damage as well as chromosomal aberrations in human lymphocytes. In an Indian series of 17 patients of herbicide poisoning, the most common symptoms were vomiting (100 %), followed by altered sensorium (59 %), oral ulceration or dysphagia (53 %), dyspnea (41 %), or loose stools (24 %) as investigated by Sandhu *et al.*, (2003). Acute respiratory distress syndrome because of paraquat usually appears 24–48 hrs. after ingestion (Singh *et al.* 1999). Triazines are reported to cause oxidative stress, endocrine disruption and fluchloralin causes chromosomal aberrations in cultured human lymphocytes (Sondhia, 2020).

There is a strong correlation for cancers of the liver, kidney, bladder/ urinary and thyroid (Fig. 6). Thyroid and bladder cancers especially seem to track with the advent of genetically engineered (GE) crops and associated glyphosate applications. Thyroid cancer seems to affect females more, while males are more susceptible to liver and kidney cancers (Swanson *et al.*, 2014).

Fig.6: Correlation between liver cancer incidence and glyphosate applications and percentage of US corn and soy crops that are genetically engineered

VI. Herbicide Residue Management Strategies

Several approaches have been utilized for mitigating the herbicidal residues in the soil. The hazards from herbicide residues in the soil can be reduced by using low dosage chemicals, reducing the levels below the maximum usage limit and unnecessary high application rates or short pre-harvest intervals (PHIs) *etc.*

Further, tillage operations, soil decontamination, crop rotation, site specific application using variable rate applicator, enhancement of herbicide degradation through biostimulation, use of non-phytotoxic oil, adjuvants, surfactants, adsorbents, protectants, antidotes, safeners, biochars, *etc.* are also various effective ways for mitigating the herbicide residues in the soil. Carbon based nano-absorbents such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene, nanocrystalline metal oxides represents a new class of material and have shown good potential in removal of various types of herbicide residues in the soil (Firozjaee *et al.*, 2018).

The amalgamation of bioaugmentation and bio-stimulation along with organic matter addition are also promising technology for biodegradation of herbicides in soil. The different approaches and methods used for the mitigation of herbicidal residues in the soil are discussed as followed.

1. Tillage

Tillage operations help in bringing deep present herbicide residues to soil surface which would aid in decontamination by volatilization (Janaki *et al.*, 2015 and Sondhia *et al.*, 2015). Ploughing with disc plough or intercultivators reduce the herbicide toxicology, as the applied herbicide is mixed to a large volume of soil and get diluted. Olson *et al.* (1998) stated that the atrazine loss was low in the chisel-disk system with incorporation compared to no till and ridge till systems.

Zablotowicz *et al.* (2007) observed the rapid degradation of fluometuron in conventional tillage (CT) compared to no-tillage (NT) soils in the 2 to 10 cm depth and found that the ryegrass cover crop systems, under NT or incorporated under CT, stimulated microbiological soil properties and promoted the herbicide degradation in surface soils. Since, most herbicide transformations in soil are mediated by microbial metabolism, modification of the soil environment and microbial populations by reduced tillage and/or cover crops can affect herbicide fate (Levanon *et al.*, 1994, Locke and Zablotowicz, 2003).

Alletto *et al.* (2011) reviewed in detail the impact of tillage practices on the sorption, degradation and movement of herbicides and found that depending on the nature of crop residues, the degradation of molecules can be affected by the presence of mulch, acetochlor, atrazine, alachlor, cyanazin and 2,4-D residues degraded faster in no till conditions. In no-tillage, vetch residues accelerated the degradation of metolachlor by from 1.5 to 3 times (Table 3).

Table 3: Sorption properties of different herbicides under different tillage practices

Herbicide	Tillage	Depth (cm)	Sorption (mg kg ⁻¹)
Acetochlor	NT	0-10	2.7
	CT	0-10	1.7
Acifluorfen	NT	0-10	0.8
	CT	0-10	0.8
Alachlor	NT	0-5	5.6
	CT	0-5	3.6
Atrazine	NT	0-15	1.7
	CT	0-15	1.4
Cyanazin	NT	0-5	3.5
	CT	0-5	2.2
Metolachlor	NT	0-5	3.5
	CT	0-5	2.0
2,4-D	NT	0-3	4.2
	CT	0-3	1.7

2. Use of optimum dose of herbicide

Expected hazards from herbicide residues can be minimized by the application of herbicide in their lowest effective dosage by which the desired weed control is achieved. Application of herbicides in bands will also reduce the total amount of herbicide to be applied. This can be practiced in line-sown crops or crops raised along ridges, such as cotton, sugarcane, sorghum, maize, *etc.* Application of atrazine at the rate of 2 kg ha⁻¹ exhibited more than 90 % atrazine degradation on 90th day in the sugarcane grown soil, whereas, the same was achieved in 180 days when the atrazine was applied @ 5 kg ha⁻¹ (Shanmugasundram *et al.*, 2005). Increase in residue and persistence of herbicides in soil with increase in quantity of application have also been reported for various herbicides (Sondhia, 2013 and Janaki *et al.*, 2015).

Sharma *et al.*, (2013) had studied effect of different doses of pretilachlor on the herbicide half life, residues, NRA and rice grain protein and concluded that using optimum dose of herbicide in rice crop resulted in higher Nitrate reductase activity (NRA), grain protein percentage, reduced herbicidal residue and halflife of pretilachlor (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of different doses of pretilachlor on the herbicide half life, residues, NRA and rice grain protein

Treatment	Half life (days)	Residues ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		NRA activity ($\mu\text{mol NO}_3$ reduced g^{-1} fresh weight hour^{-1})	Grain protein (%)
		75 DAS	90 DAS		
0.375 kg ha^{-1} (1/2 X)	11.6	BDL	BDL	0.95	9.9
0.75 kg ha^{-1} (X)	13.7	0.11 \pm 0.007 (98.2)	BDL	1.16	10.1
1.5 kg ha^{-1} (2X)	15.8	0.091 \pm 0.01 (94.1)	0.021 \pm 0.004 (98.6)	0.93	9.6
Weedy check	-	-	-	0.71	9.5
CD (5%)	-	-	-	0.23	NS

3. Using herbicides with minimum carryover potential

Herbicides with low persistence nature will have low carryover potential. Choosing herbicides with little or no carryover effect will eliminate succeeding crop injury. Metoxuron, pyrazosulfuron-ethyl and tralkoxydim were least persisting herbicides in the soil and have very little carryover potential. At Bengaluru, persistence of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl in water in transplanted rice was determined. Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl residues were found in the range of 0.0067 to 0.0022 mg kg^{-1} on 15th to 30th day. However on 45th day, it was below limit of quantification at recommended level of application (Prasad *et al.*, 2008).

4. Split application of herbicides

Ethofumesate is a selective, systemic post emergence herbicide for weed control in sugar beet. Two different doses of ethofumesate 0.99 and 1.98 kg ha^{-1} were applied as one time at 2-4 leaf stage of weeds and in three equal splits during 2, 4-6 and 8-10 leaf stage of weeds.

The results stated that split application of herbicides incurred in reduced half life and increased degradation of herbicidal residue (Table 5) in sugarbeet crop in Tamilnadu (Janaki *et al.*, 2014).

Table 5: Half life of ethofumesate in sugar beet plant and field soil under single time and split application

Treatment	Single time application - Half life (Days)	Split application - Half life (Days)
Sugarbeet plant		
T ₁ : 0.99 kg ha ⁻¹ (X)	4.20	2.30
T ₂ : 1.98 kg ha ⁻¹ (2X)	7.70	2.90
Field soil		
T ₁ : 0.99 kg ha ⁻¹ (X)	5.39	5.11
T ₂ : 1.98 kg ha ⁻¹ (2X)	9.67	5.38

5. Crop rotation

However, the crop rotation with other crops is recommended, selection of crops should be done wisely to avoid herbicide residual phytotoxicity. Crop rotation is another herbicide residue management practice that spreads the planting and herbicide application season, reducing the risk of encountering widespread herbicide runoff during a single runoff event. Ragi–cotton–sorghum is the common example of crop rotation under irrigated field conditions. Fluchloralin 0.9 kg or butachlor 0.75 kg ha⁻¹ + hand weeding at 35 DAT for ragi + sunflower (border crop), pendimethalin 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ + hand weeding on 35 DAS for cotton intercropped with onion and two manual weeding at 15 and 35 DAS for sorghum inter cropped with cowpea is the recommended weed control practice with reduced carryover effects of herbicidal residue (Wagh, 2017).

Rape seed and sugar beet being sensitive to imidazolinones (imazamox + imazethapyr) must be avoided in rotation as a succeeding crop when the previous crop was applied with these herbicides, however, maize, winter wheat and barley can be used for crop rotation (Suzer and Byuk, 2010).

Maize and millets can be used for crop rotation in the soils containing triazine residues, whereas crops like, methi, turnip, berseem and gobhi-sarson can be grown in the soil having

sulfosulfuron residue (Table 6) and berseem had increased the fodder yield under residual conditions favouring best suited crop in areas having sulfosulfuron residue (Singh and Walia 2005).

Table 6: Grain yield of vegetable pea, raya, berseem and maize grown in crop rotation with sulfosulfuron treated wheat

Treatment	Vegetable Pea (kg ha ⁻¹)	Raya (kg ha ⁻¹)	Berseem (t ha ⁻¹)	Maize (kg ha ⁻¹)
R	5135	1130	87.83	5892
2R	4661	993	80.35	5472
Control (HW)	5769	1304	85.23	6153
LSD (P=0.05)	812	111	4.77	640

R- Sulfosulfuron @ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ and **2R**- Sulfosulfuron @ 50 g a.i. ha⁻¹

6. Herbicidal rotation

Long term herbicidal rotational trail in paddy at Tamilnadu by Balasubramanian (2001) with thiobencarb @ 1.5 kg ha⁻¹, butachlor @ 1.5 kg ha⁻¹, pretilachlor @ 0.75 kg ha⁻¹ and anilophos @ 0.4 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in no residue of butachlor, pretilachlor and anilophos due to rotation of herbicide is done in rabi season. However, the carryover effect of thiobencarb residue is observed, because of using same herbicide in *rabi* season also and residues were found in soil, grain and straw, respectively (Table 7).

Comparatively, pretilachlor performed well among all the herbicides showing higher weed control efficiency and grain yield in *rabi* season (Table 8).

Table 7: Effect of herbicide rotation on thiobencarb herbicide residue in soil, grain and straw of paddy

Treatment		Soil (ppm)		Grain (ppm)		Straw (ppm)	
<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
Thiobencarb	Thiobencarb	0.189	0.193	0.002	0.002	0.022	0.026
Thiobencarb	Butachlor	0.126	-	0.002	-	0.022	-
Thiobencarb	Pretilachlor	0.131	-	0.002	-	0.021	-
Thiobencarb	Anilophos	0.123	-	0.002	-	0.021	-

Table 8: Effect of herbicide rotation on WCE and grain yield of paddy

Treatment		WCE (%)		Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	
<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
Thiobencarb	Thiobencarb	66.5	64.5	5641	4743
Thiobencarb	Butachlor	66.5	67.5	5450	4608
Thiobencarb	Pretilachlor	71.3	72.0	5688	4827
Thiobencarb	Anilophos	63.8	62.8	5371	4528
LSD (p=0.05)		-	-	238	246

8. Crop rotation with herbicide rotation

Herbicide rotation (butachlor for finger millet *fb* pendimethalin for groundnut) with crop rotation offers better option to reduce herbicidal residue both in soil and plant. The residues of butachlor and pendimethalin were below detectable level in soil after the harvest of finger millet and groundnut in long term trial and increased profits over farmers practice (Table 9) at hebbal, karnataka (Prasad *et al.*, 2010).

Table 9: Effect of herbicidal rotation on yield and savings over hand weeding in finger millet-groundnut crop rotation

Finger millet			Groundnut		
Treatment	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Savings over HW	Treatment	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Savings over HW
Butachlor @ 0.75 kg ha ⁻¹	3533	Rs. 6980 ha ⁻¹	Pendimethalin @ 1 kg ha ⁻¹	2160	Rs. 3018 ha ⁻¹

Hand weeding (HW)	3395	-	Hand weeding (HW)	2094	
CD (5 %)	320		CD (5%)	182	

9. Light irrigation after application

Continuous moist soils often result in a more rapid breakdown of herbicides due to creation of favourable conditions for microbial activity. While, controlled irrigations enhance all modes of deactivation, heavy irrigations leach herbicides out of the root zone of the crop.

Rice *et al.* (2002) stated that the saturated soil favoured the dissipation of metolachlor and the formation of soil bound residues. Significantly greater quantities of a dechlorinated metabolite were measured in the saturated surface soil compared to the unsaturated soil.

Lovell *et al.* (2002) found that the degradation of isoxaflutole was faster in soil maintained at -100 or -1500 kPa compared to that in air-dry soil. At 25 °C, the half-lives for isoxaflutole were 9.6, 2.4, and 1.5 days in air-dry, -1500 kPa and -100 kPa moisture regimes, respectively.

10. Site specific application using variable rate applicator

The interaction between herbicide chemistry and soil properties greatly affects its weed control efficacy and the potential for crop injury. Because of this, fields with significant variability in soil properties are good candidates for variable rate of application of soil-applied herbicides.

The combination of automatic tractor steering and variable rate technology is well suited for site-specific application of pre-emergence herbicides. With tractor guidance control and variable rate controllers, growers can increase the efficiency of chemical application by applying optimum rates based on soil texture (Fig. 7). These technologies have primarily been adopted by growers of major crops such as corn, wheat and soybeans (Koch and Khosla, 2007). Bauer and Schefcik (1994) found that recommended application rates of pre-emergence soil applied herbicides can vary as much as 50 % in a given field due to varying soil textures.

Kurt *et al.* (2011) studied the effectiveness of benefin herbicides in controlling weeds on vegetable crops using the variable rate technology in different textured soils and found that the use of this technology resulted in significantly less crop injury and significantly more marketable yield as compared to uniform application. In the portions of the lettuce field with loamy sand textured soils, 35 % less herbicide was applied and up to 40 % more heads were harvested.

Fig. 7 Variable rate application technology in weed management

11. Nutrient management (Organic + Inorganic sources)

Enhanced 2,4-D degradation due to the combined application of organic and inorganic source of N in transplanted rice-rice system. However, the pretilachlor degradation was stimulated and enhanced by the 100 % organic sources of nitrogen. Butachlor dissipation was rapid due to the combined application of organic and inorganic sources of N in the rice soil continuously for ten years and has been attributed to the enhanced population of microbes in soil as influenced by the organic matter addition (Janaki *et al.*, 2010).

Residues of imazethapyr as detected by HPLC in soil, soybean grain and straw are presented in (Table 10). The concentration of imazethapyr residues was found 0.0221 and 0.0190 mg g⁻¹ at harvest in soybean grain and straw, respectively in treatment which consisted of 100 % N application. However, in the other treatments residues of imazethapyr were found below detectable limits. Concentration of imazethapyr in soil was maximum (0.0134 mg g⁻¹) in treatment (100 % N + imazethapyr) and the lowest concentration of imazethapyr in soil is for 100 % NPK+ FYM+ imazethapyr, respectively. This could be due to application of FYM along with 100 % NPK. Low concentration of the imazethapyr in soil is also compensated by the increased microbial activity, which increased the rate of degradation.

Table 10: Residue of imazethapyr in soil and soybean grain and straw

Treatments	Residue ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		
	Soil	Soybean grain	Soybean Straw
50 % NPK + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0124	ND	ND
100 % NPK + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0119	ND	ND
150 % NPK + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0106	ND	ND
100 % NPK + hand weeding	<0.001	ND	ND
100 % NPK + Zn + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.011	ND	ND
100 % NP + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.011	ND	ND
100 % N + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0134	0.0221	0.0190
100 % NPK + FYM + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0093	ND	ND
100 % NPKS + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0121	ND	ND
Control + imazethapyr (100 g ha^{-1})	0.0124	ND	ND

12. Addition of organic matter

Herbicides are inactivated by various plant residues or organic matter (Table 11) incorporated into soil (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). The organic matter acts in two ways where primarily, the application of manures adsorbs the herbicide molecules in their colloidal fraction and makes them unavailable for crops and weeds and after a lag phase, microbial population thriving on organic matter starts decomposing the herbicide residues at a faster rate due to high moisture holding capacity of organic matter in soils. Meena *et al.* (2007) reported that the FYM application at 12.5 t ha^{-1} reduced the atrazine residue significantly followed by compost (12.5 t ha^{-1}) and phosphoric acid (50 ppm) application.

Residual toxicity of atrazine to the sensitive crop soybean was overcome by the application of farm yard manure @ 12.5 t ha^{-1} or compost @ 12.5 t ha^{-1} or charcoal @ 5.0 kg ha^{-1} along the seed line (Chinnusamy *et al.*, 2008).

Randhawa *et al.* (2005) found that the residues of isoproturon, 2,4-D and butachlor in the soil under rice-wheat cropping was not built up when the organic matter was continuously applied for five years.

Janaki *et al.* (2014) reported the influence of clay and organic matter on the sorption and persistence of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl in rice growing soils and suggested that the persistence of the herbicide and its residue depended on the above properties of the soil. Similarly, Arora (2017) also found that the leaching and persistence of oxyfluorfen depended on the organic matter addition through FYM in sandy clay loam soil. Sharma and Angiras (2004) observed that higher the organic matter content in soils, lesser was the persistence of atrazine and *vice versa*.

Table 11. Use of various amendments for the enhanced degradation of herbicides

Amendment	Target herbicide
Animal manure and sewage sludge	Atrazine and alachlor
Activated sludge	Atrazine and simazine
Sewage sludge and corn meal	Alachlor and trifluralin
Maize straw	Methabenzthiazuron
Dairy manure	Atrazine
Commeal, rye grass, and poultry litter	Cyanazine and fluometuron
Plant residues, ground seed, or commercial meal	Alachlor, metolachlor, atrazine and trifluralin
Cellulose, straw, and compost	Atrazine
Compost, corn stalks, corn fermentation by-product, peat, manure, and sawdust	Atrazine, trifluralin, and metolachlor
Raw olive cake	Chlorsulfuron, prosulfuron, and bensulfuron
Biogas slurry, mushroom spent compost, and farm yard manure	Atrazine
Rice straw, farm yard manure, saw dust, and charcoal	Atrazine

13. Integrated Weed Management (IWM)

Integrated weed management (IWM) involves the application of a variety of management practices to control weeds. Herbicides are used only when weed populations exceed an economic threshold level that justifies their application. Field scouting is required to monitor weed populations. Nonchemical weed control methods, such as crop rotation, cultivation, competitive hybrids, rotary hoeing and altered planting dates, are emphasized as management practices that can reduce the need for herbicides. The effectiveness of the integrated weed management using chemical and mechanical means in different crops has been studied vastly in India and also at world level. Sathiyavani and Prabhakaran (2014) reported that the pre-emergence application of metribuzin @ 0.7 kg ha⁻¹ on three days after planting (DAP) of turmeric plus hand weeding on 45 and 75 DAP for effective weed management and higher yield without phytotoxicity to crop and carryover problems.

Similarly, Sharma *et al.* (2013) found that the application of 2,4-D at three levels of 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 kg ha⁻¹ in wheat crop at 35 days after sowing persisted in soil up to 15, 45 and 75 days, respectively, however, residues of 2,4-D were found below detectable level (0.02 ppm)

in wheat grain and wheat straw. Nalini *et al.* (2010) found that the pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (38.7 %) at 2 kg ha⁻¹ + hand weeding (HW) on 45 DAS showed effective weed control in cotton without leaving any residues in the soil at the time of harvest and carryover problems to the succeeding crops, *viz.* pearl millet, cowpea and sunflower grown in sequence.

14. Growing of herbicide resistant and tolerant crops

Growing of genetically modified herbicide resistant crops in soils contaminated with the specific herbicide for which the crop was made resistant will be a viable option. Certain herbicide tolerant crops can reduce herbicide residues in a soil by absorbing and deactivating these in their tissues Eg: Maize and millets, for instance, are very good consumers of triazine herbicides. Vetiver was not affected by exposure to the herbicides, atrazine and diuron, at concentrations as high as 2,000 mg l⁻¹ (Cull *et al.*, 2000). The crops like methi, turnip, berseem and gobhi-sarson were not affected by the carryover effect of sulfosulfuron and hence can be grown in soil have sulfosulfuron residue (Singh and Walia, 2005).

15. Use of adsorbents, protectants and antidotes

They are applied to the soil, crop seed or transplanted plant to protect the crop from herbicide injury. The mode of action may be due either to deactivation or adsorption of the herbicide, preventing its absorption and translocation by the crop.

Activated charcoal has a high adsorptive capacity because of its extremely large surface area and may either be broadcasted or applied as narrow band over the seed at the time of planting. Yelverton *et al.* (1992) reported that the application of activated carbon 8 and 18 kg ha⁻¹ to the tobacco along with imazaquin and chlorimuron reduced the phytotoxicity besides increasing the yield from two to four fold.

Application of biochar is also a very good option to temporarily immobilize the herbicide residues in soil and allow the crop to escape from toxicity. The source of material used for biochar production also affects the sorption of herbicide residues. Biochar additions, even in small quantity, increased diuron sorption.

Thus, the presence of carbonaceous material, even in small amounts, can dominate sorption of organic compounds in soils (Cabrera and Spokas 2011). Similar results were obtained by Yu *et al.* (2010) for the sorption of pyrimethanil on the same soil and using the same amendments at similar rates.

The influence of biochar and its sources on herbicide dissipation is presented in table 12.

Table 12. Biochars and herbicide dissipation in soil

Herbicide	Finding
Atrazine	A lag phase of 11 days in the dissipation of atrazine in the non-amended and biochar amended silt loam soil. Later, dissipation was greater in the unamended soil.
Atrazine	Increase in the degradation in a clay soil adapted to atrazine, and amended with biochar and attributed to the stimulation of the soil microflora by the nutrients provided by biochar.
Acetochlor Isoproturon	Amending soil with biochar resulted in a DT ₅₀ of 34.5 days Biochar amendment increased the isoproturon persistence in soil with the DT ₅₀ of 2.2 days in the unamended soil to 5.6 days in the 2% (w/w) biochar amended soil.
Atrazine and trifluralin	Decreased bioavailability of the chemicals by the wheat straw biochar. Hence, choosing the appropriate application rates for biochar amended soils is essential.
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	Biochar (0.5%) amendment did not have significant effect on herbicide degradation. Half-life values in the control, 0.5% biochar amended and rice planted soils were 7, 8.6, and 10.4 days, respectively.
Fluometuron and MCPA	Not all biochar amendments will increase sorption and decrease leaching of fluometuron and MCPA. The amount and composition of the organic carbon (OC) content of the amendment, especially the soluble part (DOC), can play an important role in the sorption and leaching of these herbicides. Biochar and surface area are other important parameters to be considered for sorbent election.
MCPA	Enhanced MCPA persistence and soil toxicity in sandy soil amended with straw biochar. Also, significantly more MCPA remained after 100 days if amended with straw-derived biochar in comparison to wood-derived biochar.

16. Use of safeners

Herbicide safeners are a group of structurally diverse synthetic chemicals with the unique ability to protect crop plants from injury by certain herbicides (Farago *et al.* 1994). They are used commercially to improve herbicide selectivity between crops and weed species and can be either as a mixture with the herbicide (Table 13) or as a seed treatment to the crop seed prior to sowing (Janaki *et al.*, 2015). They act as “*bioregulators*” controlling the amount of a given herbicide that reaches its target site in an active form. A safener-induced enhancement of the metabolic detoxification of herbicides in protected plants is the most apparent mechanism for the action of all commercialized safeners. Herbicide-detoxifying enzymes such as glutathione transferases (GST), cytochrome P-450 monooxygenases (Cyt P450), esterases, and UDP-glucosyltransferases are induced by herbicide safeners. At the molecular level, safeners appear to act by activating or amplifying genes coding for these enzymes like GST (Hatzios and Wu, 1996).

Table 13: Commonly used herbicide safeners

Safners	Crop	Herbicide
Naphthalic anhydride	Maize	Thiocarbamate, Sulfonylureas, Imidazolinones, Chlorsulfuron
Dichlormid	Maize	Thiocarbamate, Sethoxydim, Clomazone
Benoxacor	Maize	Metolachlor
Dichlormid	Wheat	Diallate
Cloquintocet-mexyl	Wheat	Clodinafop-progaryl
Mefenpyrdiethyl	Wheat, Rye, Triticale, Barley	Fenoxaprop-ethyl
Fenclorim	Rice	Pretilachlor
Naphthalic anhydride	Oats	Diclofop-methyl
Cyometrinil, Fluxofenim, Oxabetrinil	Sorghum	Metolachlor
Flurazole	Sorghum	Alachlor, Acetochlor, Thiocarbamate
Flurazole	Cereals	Halosulfuron-methyl

17. Bioaugmentation

Bioaugmentation is the process of introduction of specific microorganisms aiming to accelerate the biodegradation of target compound or serving as donors of the catabolic genes. Usually this goes in pair with the biostimulation (Kanissery and Sims 2011). If appropriate biodegrading microorganisms are not present in the soil, or if microbial populations have been reduced because of contaminant toxicity, specific microorganisms can be added as “introduced organisms” to enhance the existing populations.

Microorganisms help in degradation of the herbicide compounds in the soil by utilizing them as a supply of nutrients and energy. Hence, increasing the population of herbicide degrading, pure culture bacteria by artificial means may be helpful in enhancement of herbicides in the soil. Mixture of pure cultures of microbial population have been found to be effective in enhanced metabolism of atrazine with the repeated transfer of the mixed cultures

even at the elevated concentrations (Mandelbaum *et al.*, 1993). *Rhizopus oryzae* is a potential fungal isolate that can be used for the bioremediation of alachlor from soil and the half-life values in sterile and non-sterile soil incubated with *Rhizopus oryzae* were found to be 7.2 and 8.6 days, respectively (Jaya *et al.*, 2014). Composite culture of *Bacillus* along with *Pseudomonas* and *Burkholderia* was effective in degrading atrazine by hydrolysis, dealkylation and dehydrogenation (Dutta *et al.*, 2016).

18. Phytoremediation

It is a bioremediation process that uses various types of plants to remove, transfer, stabilize, and/or destroy contaminants in the soil and groundwater. The *in situ* use of vegetation in bioremediation schemes is termed as phytoremediation which is an emerging technology for the cleanup of contaminated environments such as soil, water and sediments.

Different tolerant plants are planted at the contaminated sites which uptake the main pollutant along with other nutrients and thus changing the soil chemistry and increases microbial activity. Success of phytoremediation technique mainly depends upon the selection of proper tolerant plant and suitable soil (Arthur and Coats, 1998). Rice and Sikka (1973) observed atrazine removal of about 59 % by submerged aquatic plant. Poplar trees seemed to be effective in the rapid assimilation of ring leveled atrazine (90 %) from sandy soil in less than 9 days whereas, in clayey soil the assimilation was very poor (Burken and Schnoor, 1996). Similarly, transgenic poplars, over expressing γ -glutamylcysteine synthetase (γ ECS), could be used for phytoremediation of herbicides due to the increased GSH levels.

Santhos *et al.*, (2020) reported that *Inga edulis* had reduced the residues of atrazine and sulfentrazone herbicides in soils which is suggested to reclaim soils having these two herbicides (Table 14).

Species	Residues of atrazine (g ha ⁻¹)
<i>Inga edulis</i>	90.77
<i>Myrsine gardneriana</i>	109.39
<i>Schizolobium parahyba</i>	102.66
<i>Toona ciliate</i>	105.28
<i>Triplaris Americana</i>	102.61
<i>Trichilia hirta</i>	114.99
CD	NS
CV (%)	15.19

Table 14: Atrazine residues in soil cultivated with tree species changes for 120 days

Fig.8: Sulfentrazone residues in soil cultivated with tree species changes for 120 days

19. Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology offers many potential benefits to improve existing environmental technologies using new materials with effective performance that resulting to less consumption of energy and materials. Due to its beneficial effects, researchers and industrial communities also gained much interest in nanotechnology. Nanotechnology intervention utilizes the structures and devices with a size range from 1 nm (molecular scale) to about 100 nm (Riu *et al.*, 2006). A number of nanotechnological interventions such as carbon-based nanotubes

(CNT's), graphene, nanocrystalline metal oxides *etc.* are becoming popular in terms of herbicide residue mitigation (Iavicoli *et al.*, 2017).

Zero-valent iron nanoparticles (nZVI, diameter < 90 nm, specific surface area = 25 m² g⁻¹) have been used under anoxic conditions for the remediation of pesticides alachlor in water. While, alachlor (10, 20 and 40 mg l⁻¹) was reduced by 92–96 % within 72 hrs (Fig.9). The alachlor degradation reaction was found to obey first-order kinetics very closely and further, the reaction rate increased with increasing alachlor concentration (Bezbaruah *et al.*, 2009).

Fig.9: Degradation of alachlor treated with zero-valent iron nanoparticles over time 10 mg alachlor l⁻¹ (a), 20 mg alachlor l⁻¹ (b), 40 mg alachlor l⁻¹ (c) and first order model for alachlor degradation (d)

VII. Conclusion

Extensive use of herbicides poses far-reaching consequences and there is an essential need for efficient technologies for mitigation of residues. Herbicidal use should be done in recommended dosage so that least possible deterioration of the environment is done. Integrating practices like bioaugmentation and use of organic matter can help in residue management. Phyto-remediation is an emerging technology for the removal of herbicidal residues from the contaminated site. Therefore, mitigation strategies of herbicidal residue hazard need to be developed to lessen their effect on environment by reducing adverse impacts to less than significant levels. To avoid potential ill effects, strict and stringent regulatory mechanisms are to be developed. A critical aspect to mitigate is the implementation of best management practices which is facilitated by effective education and training programs.

VIII. Future research needs

- In India, most of the research has been done pertinent to cultural and mechanical management of herbicide residues in soil and to some extent on the split application or rotational use of herbicides. However, the research works on evaluating best herbicide rotations for cropping systems over different agro climatic zones, deactivation of herbicides utilizing the various organic sources need to be focussed.
- Enhancing the degradation by bioaugmentation and removal of contaminants from the site using the phytoremediation techniques are scanty or nil and need greater attention.
- Similarly, the effect of crop residues on the behaviour of herbicide residues in soil and environment is also very little. Hence, extensive site specific field studies will be essential to develop holistic measures for the management of herbicide residue in soil environment.

IX. References

- Alletto L, Coquet Y, Benoit P, Djilali H and Barriuso E. 2009. Tillage management effects on pesticide fate in soils – A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*. **30**: 367-400.
- Angiras NN., 2004. Weed management studies in garden pea (*Pisum sativum* sub sp. Hortens L.). *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. **36**(1): 135-137.
- Annual Report. 2009. *All India Coordinated Research Project on Weed Control*. Directorate of Weed Science Research, Jabalpur.
- Arora A, Tomar SS and Sondhia S. 2013. Efficacy of herbicides on wheat and their terminal residues in soil, grain and straw. *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. **45**(2): 109-112.
- Arora A. 2014. Evaluation of leaching behavior of oxyfluorfen in FYM amended and un-amended sandy clay loam soil. pp. 276. In: Proceedings of the Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science on Emerging Challenges in Weed Management, 15-17 February, 2014. Directorate of Weed Science Research, Jabalpur.
- Arthur EL and Coats JR. 1998. In: Pesticide Remediation in Soils and Water. Eds. P. Kearney and T. Roberts. John Wiley & Sons Ltd., Chichester, U.K. *Phytoremediation*. pp. 251- 283.

- Balasubramanian V, Anbumani S and Panneerselvam P. 2001. Effect of weed control methods on growth and yield of sunflower. *Agricultural Science Digest*. **21**(1): 31-33.
- Bauer WD and Schefcik M. 1994. Using differential GPS to improve crop yields. *GPS World*. **5**(2): 38-41.
- Bezbaruah AN, Krajangpan S, Chisholm BJ, Khan E and Ber-mundez J. 2009. Entrapment of iron nanoparticles in calcium alginate beads for groundwater remediation applications. *The Journal of Hazardous Materials*. **166**: 1339-1343.
- Bhardwaj T and Sharma JP. 2013. Impact of pesticides application in agricultural industry: an Indian scenario. *International Journal of Agricultural Science and Food Technology*. **14**: 817-822.
- Bhattacharyya A, Ganguly P, Barik SR and Kundu C. 2012. Studies on the persistence of diclosulam in soybean crop. *Pakistan Journal of Weed Science Research*. **18**:29-37.
- Burken JG and Schnoor JL. 1996. Phytoremediation: plant uptake of atrazine and role of root exudates. *Journal of Environmental Engineering*. **123**(11): 958-963.
- Cabrera MA and Spokas KA. 2011. Impacts of biochar (black carbon) additions on the sorption and efficacy of herbicides. In: *Herbicides and Environment*. Ed. A. Kortekamp. In Tech: Rijeka, Croatia. pp. 315-340.
- Chinnusamy C, Prabhakaran NK, Janaki P and Govindarajan K. 2008. Compendium on Weed Science Research in Tami Nadu (25 years). Dept. of Agronomy, TNAU, Coimbatore. 220 p.
- Choudhury PP, Singh R, Ghosh D and Sharma AR. 2016. Herbicide use in Indian agriculture. ICAR Directorate of Weed Research, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh. 110p.
- Cull RH, Hunter H and Hunter M. 2000. Application of vetiver grass technology in off-site pollution control. II. Tolerance of vetiver grass towards high levels of herbicides under wetland conditions. In: *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Vetiver*. Office of the Royal Development Projects Board, Bangkok. pp. 407-410.
- Devi PI, Thomas J and Raju RK. 2017. Pesticide consumption in India: a spatiotemporal analysis. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*. **30**:163-172.

- Dwivedi S, Saquib Q, Abdulaziz A, Al-Khedhairy, Musarrat J. 2012. Butachlor induced dissipation of mitochondrial membrane potential oxidative DNA damage and necrosis in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Toxicology*. **302**(1): 77-87.
- Farago S, Brunold C and Kreuz K. 1994. Herbicide safeners and glutathione metabolism. *Physiologia Plantarum*. **91**(3): 537-542.
- Gupta M, Garg NK, Joshi H and Sharma MP. 2012. Persistence and mobility of 2,4-D in unsaturated soil zone under winter wheat crop in sub-tropical region of India. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*. **146**(1): 60-72.
- Hatzios KK and Wu J. 1996. Herbicide safeners: Tools for improving the efficacy and selectivity of herbicides. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health Part B*. **31**(3): 545- 553.
- Iavicoli I, Leso V, Beezhold DH and Shvedova AA. 2017. Nanotechnology in agriculture: Opportunities, toxicological implications and occupational risks. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*. **329**: 96-111.
- Janaki P, Rathika S, Vellaikumar R, Prabhakaran NK and Chinnusamy C. 2010. Persistence and residue of ethofumesate and metamitron herbicides in sugar beet grown soil. In: Proceedings of National Conference on Challenges in Weed Management in Agro-Ecosystems- Present Status and Future Strategies. pp. 240-241.
- Janaki P, Chinnusamy C, Radhika S, Prabhakaran NK and Senthil K. 2014. Field dissipation of ethofumesate under different methods of application in sugar beet field, pp. 285. In: Proceedings of the Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science on Emerging Challenges in Weed Management. 15-17 February, 2014. Directorate of Weed Science Research, Jabalpur.
- Janaki P, Mohana Sundram K, Chinnusamy C and Sakthivel N. 2015. Determination of residues of metribuzin in soil and sugarcane by QuEChERS. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*. **27**(10): 3692-3696.
- Jaya M, Singh SB, Kulshrestha G and Arya S. 2014. Microbial degradation of alachlor using a native fungal strain. In: Proceedings of the Biennial Conference of Indian Society of

- Weed Science on Emerging Challenges in Weed Management. 15-17 February, 2014. Directorate of Weed Science Research, Jabalpur. pp. 279.
- Kadivar MR, Muchhadiya RM, Gohil BS and Kumawat PD. 2023. Evaluating the safety of herbicide by bioassay techniques: A review. *International Journal of Research Culture Society* **7**(12): 84-91.
- Kanissery RG and Sims GK. 2011. Biostimulation for the enhanced degradation of herbicides in soil. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*. (doi:10.1155/2011/843450). Available online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2011/843450>
- Koch B and Khosla R. 2007. The role of precision agriculture in cropping systems. *Journal of Crop Production*. **9**: 361- 381.
- Kurt DN, Siemens MC and Sanchez PA. 2011. Integrating variable rate technologies for soil-applied herbicides in Arizona vegetable production. Available online at www.cals.arizona.edu/pubs/crops/az1538.pdf.
- Levanon DJ, Meisinger J, Codling EE and Starr JL. 1994. Impact of tillage on microbial activity and the fate of pesticides in upper soil. *Water Air Soil Pollution*. **72**: 179-237.
- Locke MA and Zablutowicz RM. 2003. Pesticides in soil: benefits and limitations to soil quality. In: *Managing Soil Quality*. Eds. P. Schjonning, B.T. Christenson, S. Elmholt. C.A.B.I., Oxon, UK. pp. 239-260.
- Lovell ST, Sims GK and Wax LM. 2002. Degradation of isoxaflutole in soil. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. **50**(20): 5626-5633.
- Mandelbaum RT, Wackett LP and Allan DL. 1993. Mineralization of the s-triazine ring of atrazine by stable bacterial mixed cultures. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. **59**(3): 1695-1701.
- Marfo TD, Datta R, Pathan SI, Vranová V. 2019. Herbicides and nutrient cycling. *Journal of Agricultural Chemistry*. **11**: 53.
- Meena S, Chinnusamy C and Varsney JG. 2007. Status report on herbicide residue. Dept. of Agronomy, TNAU, Coimbatore.1-30 p.

- Meena RS, Meena VS, Meena SK and Verma, JP. 2016. Herbicides and soil enzyme activities. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. **102**: 560-561.
- Mishra AK, Mahinda AJ, Shinjo H, Jat ML, Singh A and Funakawa, S. 2017. Impact of herbicides on soil carbon mineralization. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*. **69**: 307-320.
- Motta EV, Raymann K and Moran NA. 2018. Glyphosate perturbs the gut microbiota of honey bees. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. **115**(41): 10305-10310.
- Muniappa VT, Manjunatha V, Babu VS and Shivkumar HR. 1995. Efficacy of post emergent herbicides on control of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes* Mart.) and their effect on fishes. *World Weeds*. **2**: 117-121.
- Nair RS, Paulmurugan R and Wilsanand V. 2005. Genotoxic effects of commonly used pesticides of south india in human lymphocytes. *Pollution research*. **24**(1): 7-12.
- Nalini K, Muthukrishan P, Chinnusamy C and Janaki P. 2010. Pre-emergence herbicide pendimethalin residue in cotton cultivated soil. In: Proceedings of the Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science on Recent Advances in Weed Science Research, 25-26 February, 2010, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Raipur. pp. 189.
- Naveen DV, Gowda RC and Mamatha B. 2012. Field studies on persistence of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl in soil, ground water and residues in transplanted rice. *Asian Journal of Soil Science*. **89**(5): 1032-1036.
- Norton R. 2013. Focus on calcium: Its role in crop production. International Plant Nutrition Institute. GRDC Updates Pap. Available online: https://grdc.com.au/resources-and-publications/grdc-update-papers/tab-content/grdc_updatepapers/2013/02/focus_on-calcium-its-role-in-crop-production (accessed on 25 September 2020).
- Olson BLS, Regehr DL, Janssen KA and Barnes PL. 1998. Tillage system effects on atrazine loss in surface water runoff. *Weed Technology*. **12**: 646-651.
- Panneerselvam N, Sinha S and Shanmugam G. 1995. Genotoxicity of the herbicide fluchloralin on human lymphocytes in vitro, chromosomal aberration and micronucleus tests. *Mutation Research Genetic Toxicology*. **34**(1&2): 69-72.

- Pimentel D. 1995. Amounts of pesticides reaching target pests: environmental impacts and ethics. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*. **8**: 17-29.
- Prasad TVR, Kumar VK, Denesh GR and Sanjay MT. 2010. Long-term herbicide usage on weed shift and productivity in transplanted finger millet- groundnut cropping system in southern Karnataka. *The Journal of Crop and Weed*. **6**(1): 44-48.
- Rahman MM. 2020. Potential environmental impacts of herbicides used in agriculture. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*. **3**(1): 266-269.
- Randhawa SK, Singh T and Singh S. 2005. Effect of organic matter on the persistence of herbicide in rice-wheat cropping system. In: Proceedings of National Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science, 6- 9 April, 2005, PAU, Ludhiana. pp. 283-284.
- Reddy KN and Reddy H. 2010. Pesticide residues in surface water of lakes around hyderabad, India. *Pesticide Research Journal*. **22**(2): 111-115.
- Rice CP and Sikka HC. 1973. Fate of dieldrin in selected species of marine algae. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*. **9**: 116-123.
- Rice PJ, Anderson TA and Coats JR. 2002. Degradation and persistence of metolachlor in soil: effects of concentration, soil moisture, soil depth and sterilization. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*. **21**(12): 2640-2648.
- Rose MT, Cavagnaro TR, Scanlan CA, Rose TJ, Vancov T, Kimber S, Kennedy IR, Kookana RS and Van Zwieten L. 2016. Impact of herbicides on soil biology and function. *Advances in Agronomy*. **136**: 133-220.
- Rose MT, Van Zwieten L, Zhang P, McGrath G, Seymour N, Scanlan C. and Rose T. 2019. Herbicide residues in soil-What is the scale and significance. *GRDC project code: DAN00180, 12*.
- Sandhu JS, Dhiman A, Mahajan R and Sandhu P. 2003. Outcome of paraquat poisoning -a five-year study. *Indian Journal of Nephrology*. **13**: 64-68.

- Santos E, Silva Filho, Barroso G, Rocha B and Possato E. 2020. Tolerance and remedial potential of trees submitted to atrazine and sulfentrazone in the rhizosphere. *International Journal of Phytoremediation*. **22**(1): 78-86.
- Sathiyavani E and Prabhakaran NK. 2014. Performance of pre and post-emergence herbicides on weed flora and yield of turmeric. *Trends in Biosciences*. **7**(12): 1350-1353.
- Sebiomo A, Ogundero VW and Bankole SA. 2011. Effect of four herbicides on microbial population, soil organic matter and dehydrogenase activity. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. **10**(5): 770-778.
- Senarathna L and Eddleston MF. 2009. Prediction of outcome after paraquat poisoning by measurement of the plasma paraquat concentration. *An International Journal of Medicine*. **102**(4): 251-259.
- Shanmugasundaram R, Kandasamy OS and Chinnusamy C. 2005. Impact of herbicide application on soil physicochemical properties and its residue in rice-rice cropping system. In: Proceedings of National Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science, 6-9 April, 2005, PAU, Ludhiana. pp. 290-291.
- Sharma N, Sharma S, Kumar S and Joshi R. 2013. Dissipation and harvest time residue studies of 2,4-D in soil and wheat crop. *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. **45**(1): 68-70.
- Shobha S. 2012. Persistence of herbicide residues in soil, water and food chain. In: Compendium of Training Manual on Biotic and Abiotic Resource Management for Eco-friendly and Sustainable Agriculture. Ed. Rawat Ak, Sachdanad B, Diwedi BL and Thakur RK. pp 96-99.
- Silva V, Montanarella L, Jones A, Fernández-Ugalde O, Mol HG, Ritsema CJ and Geissen, V. 2018. Distribution of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in agricultural topsoils of the European Union. *Science of the Total Environment*. **621**: 1352-1359.
- Singh M and Walia US. 2005. Studies on carryover effects of sulfosulfuron on the succeeding crops. In: Proceedings of National Biennial Conference of Indian Society of Weed Science, 6-9 April, 2005, PAU, Ludhiana. pp. 300-301.

- Singh MK, Singh NK and Singh SP. 2020. Impact of herbicide use on soil microorganisms. *Plant Responses to Soil Pollution*. **2**: 179-194.
- Singh SB, Yaduraju NT and Kulshrestha G. 1999. Terminal residues of fluazifop-p-butyl in soybean. *Annals of Plant Protection Sciences*. **7**(1): 87-90.
- Sondhia S. 2007. Herbicides residues in soil, water and food chain. In: *Annual Report*. National Research Centre for Weed Science Jabalpur. pp.7-24.
- Sondhia S. 2008. Persistence of metsulfuron-methyl in wheat crop and soil. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. **147**(1-3): 463-469.
- Sondhia S. 2009. Persistence of metsulfuron-methyl in paddy field and detection of its residues in crop produce. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*. **83**(6): 799- 802.
- Sondhia S and Dixit A. 2012. Bioefficacy and persistence of ethoxysulfuron in rice. *ORYZA- An International Journal on Rice*. **49**(3): 178-182.
- Sondhia S. 2013. Dissipation of pendimethalin in the soil of field pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and detection of terminal residues in plants. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health*. **48**(12): 1045-1048.
- Sondhia S. 2014. Herbicides residues in soil, water, plants and non-targeted organisms and human health implications: an Indian perspective. *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. **46**(1): 66-85.
- Sondhia S, Khankhane PJ, Singh PK and Sharma AR. 2015. Detection of imazethapyr residues in field soil and plants under soybean grown area following an application to soybean. *Journal of Pesticide Science*. **40**(3): 106-110.
- Sondhia S. 2018. Herbicide residue research in India. In: Sondhia S, Choudhury PP, Sharma AR (eds). Springer, Singapore, pp. 29-104.
- Sondhia S. 2020. Leaching of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl in a sandy loam soil under natural rains in field lysimeters. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*. **7**(1): 313-318.
- Suntres ZE. 2002. Role of antioxidants in paraquat toxicity. *Toxicology*. **180**(1): 65-77.

- Swanson NL, Leu A, Abrahamson J and Wallet B. 2014. Genetically engineered crops, glyphosate and the deterioration of health in the United States of America. *Journal of Organic Systems*. **9**(2): 6-37.
- Tilak KS, Veeraiah P, Thathaji and Butchiram MS. 2007. Toxicity studies of butachlor to the freshwater fish *Channa punctata* (Bloch). *Journal of Environmental Biology*. **28**(2): 485-487.
- Trappe JM, Molina R, Castellano M. 1984. Reactions of mycorrhizal fungi and mycorrhiza formation to pesticides. *Annual Review of Phytopathology*. **22**:331-359.
- VanBruggen AH, Finckh MR, He M, Ritsema CJ, Harkes P, Knuth D and Geissen V. 2021. Indirect effects of the herbicide glyphosate on plant, animal and human health through its effects on microbial communities. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*. **9**: 763917.
- Vision 2050. 2015. *Indian Council on Agricultural Research*, Directorate of Weed Science Research, Jabalpur.
- Wagh RM. 2017. Management of Herbicide Residues in Soil. *International Archive of Applied Sciences and Technology*. **8**(3): 84-87.
- Wang LD, Wang XY, Di SS, Qi PP, Sun YH, Yan XW and Wang XQ. 2018. Enantioselective analysis and degradation of isofenphos-methyl in vegetables by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. **25**: 18772-18780.
- Yadav A, Bhatnagar A and Kaur M. 2013. Aberrations in the chromosomes of *Cirrhinus mrigala* (Hamilton) upon exposure to butachlor. *Iranian Journal of Toxicology*. **7**(21): 858-865.
- Yelverton FH, Douglas worsham A and Peedin GF. 1992. Activated carbon reduces tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) injury from soil applied herbicides. *Weed Technology*. **6**: 310-316.

Yu XY, Pan LG, Ying GG and Kookana RS. 2010. Enhanced and irreversible sorption of pesticide pyrimethanil by soil amended with biochars. *Journal of Environmental Science*. **22**: 615-620.

Zablotowicz RM, Locke MA and Gaston LA. 2007. Tillage and cover effects on soil microbial properties and fluometuron degradation. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*. **44**(1): 27-35.